

Expression analysis and co-localization imaging of Jump In™ T-REx™ HEK293 WT-OE cell pools

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Protocol description

The Method uses HEK293TrexR4 cells (=wt) cells and genetically engineered variants (wt OE, KD, other) to provide a basis for expression analysis and to detect the localization of SLC-HA-Strep-tag in cellular compartments. This protocol describes the physical preparation of microscopic samples. Image analysis with respect to compartmental co-localization of the SLCs respectively their detection tags will be covered separately.

Therefore, we describe how an HA Tag is co-stained with Hoechst 33342 and specific compartment markers for Golgi, Lysosomes, ER, Mitochondria, Cell Membrane, Peroxisomes, Endosomes and Cytoplasm in order to either measure the total intensity of expressed SLC-HA tag protein per cell or give estimates on their cellular distribution. We chose a 60x magnification using water immersion objectives and a well bottom with 192um COC film thickness to provide high quality images. For compatibility reasons also 20x images are recorded using HCS cell mask stains as a backdrop to find cytoplasmic outlines.

Materials

Biological materials:	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ HEK293 Trex R4 wt SLC-OE▪ Laminin 5-2-1 (Biolamina Cat.no. LN521 Conc.100ug/mL)▪ CD107b (LAMP-2) mAb (H4B4), AlexaFluor488 (ThermoFisherScientific #53-1078-42)▪ Mouse mAb PMP70 (Sigma #SAB42000181-200uL)▪ Mouse mAb KDEL MAB (10C3) (Enzolifesciences #ADI-SPA-827-F)▪ Mouse mAb α-Tubulin (D3U1W) (Cell Signalling Technology #86298S)▪ Rabbit pAb GOLGB1/Giantin (Novus #NBP1-91938)▪ Rabbit mAb RAB9A (SR45-05) (Novus #NBP2-67331)▪ Rabbit mAb NaK ATPase (Abcam #76020)▪ Goat pAb anti HA-tag (Novus #NB600-362) <p style="text-align: center;">▲CRITICAL This antibody is sensitive to temperature changes and should always be kept on ice or 4°C. It should not be used for more than 3 months.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Mouse mAb HA-Tag (ThermoFisherScientific #26183-1MG)▪ Donkey anti-Mouse IgG (H+L) Highly Cross-Adsorbed Secondary Antibody, Alexa Fluor Plus 488 (ThermoFisherScientific #A32766-1MG)▪ Donkey anti-Rabbit IgG (H+L) Highly Cross-Adsorbed Secondary Antibody, Alexa Fluor Plus 488 (ThermoFisherScientific #A32790-1MG)▪ Donkey anti-Rabbit IgG (H+L) Highly Cross-Adsorbed Secondary Antibody, Alexa Fluor Plus 555 (ThermoFisherScientific #A32794-1MG)
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Donkey anti-Mouse IgG (H+L) Highly Cross-Adsorbed Secondary Antibody, Alexa Fluor Plus 555 (ThermoFisherScientific #A32773-1MG) ▪ Donkey anti-Goat IgG (H+L) Highly Cross-Adsorbed Secondary Antibody, Alexa Fluor Plus 647 (ThermoFisherScientific #A32849-1MG).
Reagents:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ DPBS+Ca+Mg (ThermoFisherScientificGibco Cat.no. 14040133) ▪ DMEM (Thermo Scientific # 31966) ▪ FCS h.i., dialyzed (Amimed # 2-01F17-I) ▪ NEAA (100x) (Thermo Scientific # 11140-035) ▪ Hepes (1M) (Thermo Scientific # 15630-056) ▪ Penicillin / Streptomycin (PS) (100x) (Thermo Scientific # 15140-122) ▪ Digitonin (Thermo Scientific #407565000) ▪ Triton-X100 (Thermo Scientific #85111) ▪ Paraformaldehyde (Electron Microscopy Sciences 32% w/v #EMS15714-S) ▪ Doxycyclin-hydrochloride (MerckSigmaAldrich D3447-500MG) ▪ Hoechst 33342 (Thermo Scientific # H3570) ▪ HCS Cellmask DeepRed (Thermo Scientific # 32721) ▪ Mitotracker Orange CMTMRos (Thermo Scientific # M7510)
Equipment:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Costar #4518 COC HCI 384 well microplates ▪ Imager with > 4 distinct excitation and emission wavelengths. Yokogawa CV7000 (Yokogawa Instruments, Japan) and 60x, Water immersion objectives. 405,488,561 and 647nm Laser ▪ Washer Bionex DW4 with 384 well dispense and aspiration heads ▪ Multichannel pipette: E1-ClipTip Matrix 10-300µL Electronic Adjustable Tip Spacing Multichannel Equalizer Pipettes (ThermoFisherScientific #4672080BT) <p>▲CRITICAL CHOICE Precise control over dispensing parameters is necessary. A washer, which allows the adjustment of dispensing pressure /flow rates, volumes and aspiration heights, is preferred over manual pipet based processes.</p>

Reagents setup

Cellmedium (Thawing medium from HEK293 TrexR4 manual):

90% DMEM (ThermoFisherScientific # 31966)

10% FCS h.i., dialyzed (Amimed # 2-01F17-I)

1% NEAA (100x) (ThermoFisherScientific # 11140-035)

2.5% Hepes (1M) (ThermoFisherScientific # 15630-056)

1% Penicillin / Streptomycin (PS) (100x) (ThermoFisherScientific # 15140-122)

3x Perm/Block buffer:

68% DPBS+Ca+Mg (ThermoFisherScientific # 14040133)

30% FCS h.i.

0.3% Digitonin

0.05% Triton-X100

2% PS

3x Antibody buffer:

Mix Perm/Block (20%) and Medium (80%) (v/v)

Procedure

▪ Part A of protocol / day 1

Coating micro well plates with Laminin and seeding cells

1. Dilute Laminin 1:150 in PBS+Ca+Mg and add a volume that covers the bottom of the plate 6 μ L/ well in Costar #4518, remove bubbles by quick centrifugation and incubate for >90min at 37 °C.
2. Add 60 μ L of thawing medium and aspirate and leave 25 μ L in the well
3. Add Cell suspension to yield an 80 % confluent cell layer 48 h later

▲CRITICAL STEP SLC-Pools Cells have very varying generation times. Thorough planning and measurement of individual generation times is recommended. Alternatively, cells can be grouped into fast and slow dividing cells. Cells should not be too confluent to spread a maximal area and make detection of cellular components easier.

4. Incubate until cells have attached, usually after 6h then add 1 μ g/mL Doxycycline for 22 h (Doxycycline maybe titrated to lower concentrations if toxicity becomes a concern) according to layout into respective rows. Leave enough rows without induction for a good window between induced and non-induced.

▪ Part B of protocol / day 2

5. Wash out Doxycycline by aspirating the wells to 20 μ L adding incremental volumes of Medium to reach a total volume of 80 μ L. Repeat 6 cycles. At the End aspirate to 60 μ L well volume. Then incubate cells for another 18 h at 37 °C / 5 % CO₂

▲CRITICAL STEP Washing cells too harshly will result in disruption of the cell layer and loss of cells. Empty fields create additional work on the analysis side and should be avoided.

▪ Part C of protocol / day 3

6. **Mitotracker Orange CMTMRos:** Aspirate to 30 μ L well volume and incrementally add a total of 15 μ L Mitotracker Red CMTMRos \bullet 1:15000 final dilution in thawing medium. Add Mitotracker to the wells that will later receive Setup no.3* staining. Incubate for 30 min at 37 $^{\circ}$ C / 5 % CO₂.
7. Fixation: Aspirate to 25 μ L well volume and incrementally add a total of 12.5 μ L 3x PFA solution to yield 3.5 % final. Fix for 25min at 37 $^{\circ}$ C.
8. Wash cells 6 x with PBS+Ca+Mg. Asp to 20 μ L and incrementally add 60 μ L PBS, repeat 6 times.

II PAUSE POINT. Cells may be washed only 2x and plates stored up to 2days at 4 $^{\circ}$ C. On the day of continuing the protocol 4 more washes may be performed.

9. Permeabilization / Blocking: Aspirate to 25 μ L well volume and incrementally add a total of 12.5 μ L 3x PermBlock buffer. Incubate 30min at 37 $^{\circ}$ C.
10. Wash by aspirating the wells to 20 μ L adding incremental volumes of Medium to reach a total volume of 80 μ L. Repeat 2 cycles. At the End aspirate to 25 μ L well volume.
11. Primary Staining: Add a volume of 12.5 μ L 3x Primary Solutions in antibody buffer prepared according to table below. Incubate >120min at 37 $^{\circ}$ C

Tip. Using an electronic adjustable tip spacing multichannel equalizer pipette at low speed and transferring solutions from stock tubes into the respective 384 well plate wells saves dead volume, is accurate and preserves workers from health problems through strain.

Staining setup no.	3x Primary Solution	Final dilution in assay	3x Secondary Solution	Final dilution in assay
1	goat-antiHA-Tag \bullet 1:250	(\bullet 1:750)	Hoechst 33342 \bullet 1:1000 Donkey anti goat Alexa488 \bullet 1:200 HCS Cellmask DeepRed \bullet 1:20000	(\bullet 1:3000) (\bullet 1:600) (\bullet 1:60000)
2	Mouse-antiHA-Tag \bullet 1:250	(\bullet 1:750)	Hoechst 33342 \bullet 1:1000 Donkey anti mouse Alexa488 \bullet 1:200 HCS Cellmask DeepRed \bullet 1:20000	(\bullet 1:3000) (\bullet 1:600) (\bullet 1:60000)
3*	goat-antiHA-Tag (\bullet 1:250)	(\bullet 1:750)	Hoechst 33342 (\bullet 1:1000) mouseLamp2-Alexa488 (\bullet 1:200) Donkey anti Goat Alexa647 (\bullet 1:200)	(\bullet 1:3000) (\bullet 1:600) (\bullet 1:600)
4	mouse-antiPMP70 (\bullet 1:300)	(\bullet 1:900) (\bullet 1:900) (\bullet 1:750)	Hoechst 33342 (\bullet 1:1000) Donkey anti mouse Alexa488 (\bullet 1:200)	(\bullet 1:3000) (\bullet 1:600) (\bullet 1:600) (\bullet 1:600)

	rabbit-NaKATPase (♣1:300) goat-antiHA-Tag (♣1:250)		Donkey anti Rabbit Alexa555 (♣1:200) Donkey anti Goat Alexa647 (♣1:200)	
5	Mouse-anti-KDel (♣1:300) rabbit-anti-Giantin (♣1:300) goat-antiHA-Tag (♣1:250)	(♣1:900) (♣1:900) (♣1:750)	Hoechst 33342 (♣1:1000) Donkey anti mouse Alexa488 (♣1:200) Donkey anti Rabbit Alexa555 (♣1:200) Donkey anti Goat Alexa647 (♣1:200)	(♣1:3000) (♣1:600) (♣1:600) (♣1:600)
6	rabbit-anti-Rab9a (1:300) mouse anti β - Tubulin (1:300) goat-antiHA-Tag (♣1:250)	(♣1:900) (♣1:900) (♣1:750)	Hoechst 33342 ♣1:1000 Donkey anti rabbit Alexa488 (♣1:200) Donkey anti Mouse Alexa555 (♣1:200) Donkey anti Goat Alexa647 (♣1:200)	(♣1:3000) (♣1:600) (♣1:600) (♣1:600)

▲ CRITICAL STEP Optimal staining dilutions may depend on antibody lot numbers, sensitivity of the microscope, washing efficiency and various others. A particular optimization maybe necessary.

|| PAUSE POINT. Cells may be stored up to 1day at 4 °C.

12. Wash by aspirating the wells to 20 μ L adding incremental volumes of Medium to reach a total volume of 80 μ L. Repeat 2 cycles. At the End aspirate to 25 μ L well volume.
13. Secondary Staining: Add a volume of 12.5 μ L 3x Secondary Solutions in antibody buffer according to table above using the adjustable tip spacing multichannel equalizer pipette. Incubate 90min at 37 °C.

♣ Tip. Spinning down secondary solutions at 10000 g for 2 min and sterile filtering of antibody solutions can minimize spottiness of the staining. Reordering should be considered.

14. Wash cells 6x with PBS+Ca+Mg. Asp to 20 μ L and incrementally add 60 μ L PBS, 2%PenStrep, repeat 6 times.

15. Seal plate

|| PAUSE POINT. Cells may be stored up to 2days at 4 °C. Longer storage increases the risk of detaching cells.

♣ Tip. Addition of PenStrep minimizes the risk of contamination and poses lower health risks than azide.

16. Image setup no. 1&2 (HA-tag, with and without Doxycycline induction) with 20x objective for expression level image analysis. And 60x, water immersion for localization analysis, choose optics and set exposure times such, that crosstalk is minimal. In case of a limited intensity range, image respective wells with separate settings.

17. Inspection of localization images. The assessment was conducted visually. Images of individual channels were scaled to comparable intensities and scores attributed according to the intensity per individual compartment over the total intensity and a confidence score from 1 to 5, with 5 showing the highest confidence and values below 3 being questionable.
18. Experiment definition files were created, linking image metadata with experimental metadata, to allow for image visualization and analysis. pdf-summary reports were created in addition to document visual inspection statements.

Additional notes

Typical 384 well experiment layout

Setup no.	SLC1		SLC2		SLC3		SLC4		SLC5		SLC6		SLC7		SLC8		SLC9		SLC10		SLC11		SLC12			
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24		
A																									Doxycycline for 22h, No Doxycycline for 18h	
1																										
2																										
3*																										
4																										
5																										
6																										
L																										
M																										
1																										No Induction
2																										
P																										

3* Mitotracker CMTMRos is pipetted before fixation

Data availability

<https://re-solute.eu/resources/dashboards/imaging>

Please write to contact@re-solute.eu in case of questions or errors.